

On the Challenge of Sound Code for Operating Systems

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Abstract

The memory-safe systems programming language Rust is gaining more and more attention in the operating system development communities, as it provides memory safety without sacrificing performance or control. However, these safety guarantees only apply to the *safe* subset of Rust, while bare-metal programming requires some parts of the program to be written in *unsafe* Rust. Writing abstractions for these parts of the software that are *sound*, meaning that they guarantee the absence of undefined behavior and thus uphold the invariants of safe Rust, can be challenging. Producing sound code, however, is essential to avoid breakage when the code is used in new ways or the compiler behavior changes.

In this paper, we present common patterns of unsound abstractions derived from the experience of reworking soundness in our kernel. During this process, we were able to remove over 400 unsafe expressions while discovering and fixing several hard-to-spot concurrency bugs along the way.

CCS Concepts: • **Software and its engineering** → **General programming languages; Operating systems; Embedded software; Abstraction, modeling and modularity; Synchronization; Software reliability; Software usability; Multi-paradigm languages; Language features.**

Keywords: memory safety, soundness, operating system, systems programming, Rust, safe, unsafe

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1 Introduction

Ever since C's creation in the 1970s, C and, later on, C++ have been the dominant languages for systems programming. Unfortunately, both are notorious for their error-prone manual memory management. In fact, typically, more than 65 % of all security vulnerabilities in large software projects written in these non-memory-safe languages are caused by memory unsafety [1–4]. Rust is a new memory-safe systems-programming language that has gained a lot of momentum recently [5–7]. One of the most relevant factors for this success (as also pointed out by the original author of the language [8]) is the novel approach to memory management through a sophisticated type system and the borrow checker, enabling memory safety without sacrificing control over the memory. Both factors enable shifting computational effort on memory management to compile time, unlike, for example, languages like Java and Go, which approach this problem at run time by utilizing garbage collection.

These and other features make it a very attractive choice for bare-metal programs. Unsurprisingly, plenty of operating system projects have chosen this language in the past few years. Among the most notable examples are the Redox [9] general-purpose OS, as well as the embedded operating systems TockOS [10], Drone OS [11], and Hubris [12]. New operating system concepts were also implemented in Rust, for instance in the TheseusOS [13] or RedLeaf [14] projects. Another area of operating systems written in Rust are single-address-space operating systems. One such project is the Nebulet [15] microkernel that can run WebAssembly applications. Additionally, there are numerous OS projects in the hobby and self-education area [16–22].

Writing bare-metal applications such as operating systems in Rust requires the use of *unsafe* Rust, which allows certain necessary low-level operations that are not possible in *safe* Rust, for instance when configuring the hardware by means

of specialized assembly instructions or memory-mapped register accesses. In these cases, the safety guarantees of Rust have to be upheld manually, and the compiler cannot guarantee the absence of undefined behavior. The guaranteed absence of undefined behavior in Rust code is referred to as *soundness*. This is an essential characteristic for operating systems, as crashes and vulnerabilities must be prevented at all costs.

In our own unikernel project, Hermit [23], we have suffered from some spurious bugs, that could not occur in safe Rust. Disabling compiler optimizations that particularly rely on the absence of undefined behavior provided a mitigation, but has also encouraged us to rework several parts of the kernel with an emphasis on the soundness. We scrutinized several parts of the code and found multiple issues regarding soundness. In this paper, we will discuss common soundness issues we found in this process and illustrate patterns of approaches to solving them.

2 Background

Memory safety is an essential condition for soundness. To be memory-safe, software must satisfy two requirements [24]: The software never uses memory that was not allocated for it, and the software never executes instructions that were not generated for it. This implies thread safety (the absence of data races) for abstractions that depend on data consistency for memory safety, which includes most of Rust's standard library. This includes security against external control flow and memory access manipulation and safety from internal memory misuse, that may cause the program to break one of the conditions. Specifically, breaking these requirements can result in bugs like *use-after-free*, *double-free*, *out-of-bounds*, or *return-oriented programming*.

2.1 Safe Rust and Unsafe Rust

To understand how to write sound code in Rust, it is necessary to briefly explain a few of the core concepts of Rust.

The language distinguishes between mutable and non-mutable variables. The compiler tracks each variable's mutability and prevents any writes to non-mutable variables. This is encoded explicitly in safe Rust's pointer type: mutable and non-mutable references. Functions may take mutable references, and callers have to specify *borrowing* data mutably when calling such functions.

A strong type system enables Rust's concept of *ownership*. Every value has exactly one owner, and if the owner goes out of scope, the value is freed (RAII principle). Rust allows the creation of references to variables but imposes two restrictions: First, there can be only one mutable reference or multiple shared references at the same time. This makes mutation and aliasing without synchronization impossible. Second, references are only valid as long as the value lives. This means you cannot use a reference after the source has

been moved. These rules are enforced at compile-time by the *borrow checker* to prevent invalid memory accesses as well as data races.

Rust has the **unsafe** keyword, which enables actions for which the compiler cannot check Rust's safety requirements, and it is up to the programmer to ensure valid behavior. These actions are: raw pointer dereferencing, mutation of static items (global variables), calls to unsafe functions, implementation of unsafe traits, and access to unions. It is impossible to write an operating system kernel in *safe* Rust alone; some degree of *unsafe* Rust is necessary. To create a memory management system, for example, raw pointers have to be used to modify the hardware.

2.2 Undefined Behavior in Rust

Compilers optimize programs with the assumption that they are free of undefined behavior. This means programs that do contain undefined behavior may contain broken invariants after optimization. Formally speaking, a program with undefined behavior is useless from a language perspective since it is not well-defined. From this perspective, the compiler's output may as well be random. For Rust, the absence of undefined behavior is essential, since the language gains its memory safety property from well-defined and upheld safety invariants.

Safe Rust guarantees the absence of any kind of undefined behavior (formally proven for most parts of the language in [25]). When writing unsafe Rust code, one must uphold Rust's *soundness property*: "no matter what, safe Rust can't cause undefined behavior." [26] To be able to reason about this, one has to create *sound* abstractions for unsafe code that cannot be used to cause undefined behavior, or, if that is not possible, mark the abstraction as unsafe and document all the invariants that this code depends upon.

It is important to mention that the fact that a program does not appear to misbehave does not mean it is sound or free of undefined behavior. Any change to how an unsafe abstraction is used or an upgrade of the compiler might bring forth such issues. Thus, striving for more soundness is essential for using Rust's core strengths.

3 Related Work

When it comes to the analysis of Rust as a programming language for operating systems and specific guidelines for programming these, we found the following work: In [27], Levy et al. wrote a paper about their learnings on writing their TockOS operating system in Rust. The main topics were the limitations of the ownership concept regarding hardware peripherals, the challenges of having multiple shared references to software constructs like the network stack, and the limitations of closures regarding lifetimes and ownership. As TockOS is an embedded OS, the challenges presented are somewhat specific to this design, as there is no

real application-operating system boundary and instead of threads and processes, closures are used.

The same authors took a more general approach in [28] and also identified a set of code pieces that fundamentally require *unsafe* code: context switches, memory-mapped I/O, memory allocation, user space buffers for OS interaction, interrupt/exception handlers, concurrency, and—specific to their paper—the TakeCell abstraction. In a brief case study, this paper explains software constructs to safely approach some classical patterns for (embedded) operating systems. In contrast to this paper, Levy et al. focus more on the general terms and only implicitly consider the soundness of their abstractions.

The following documents and guidelines exist for writing unsafe Rust code: the authoritative *Rust Reference* [29], the work-in-progress *Unsafe Code Guidelines Reference* [30], and the historical *Rustonomicon* [26].

A similar approach to our work was taken by Qin et al. in [31], where safety issues and their impact on real-world Rust programs were investigated. This can be seen as a top-down approach, where bugs in existing software are found and explained. We focus more on soundness than actual bugs, and additionally, we highlight some techniques and patterns to avoid these kinds of problems in the first place.

4 Typical Soundness Issues

As explained in subsection 2.2, it is important to find sound abstractions for unsafe code, prevent undefined behavior, and avoid excessive use of unsafety: In the following, we describe four typical soundness issues we found in our codebase and present our approaches for reducing unsafe code and avoiding undefined behavior.

As already explained in subsection 2.2, if it is not possible to assert the absence of undefined behavior within an abstraction, the abstraction can declare itself unsafe and shift the responsibility to the caller. Pushing this principle to the maximum by marking every aspect of our abstractions as unsafe would basically remove the whole code from any soundness considerations. However, this bypasses the memory-safety functions of Rust, basically setting it back on the same level as C or C++ in that regard.

Taking for granted that this is not desirable, it is necessary to formulate all the safety requirements for any kind of unsafe API. Otherwise, it becomes impossible to use this API correctly, and the calling code needs to be declared unsafe itself without any explanation. We therefore call this kind of unsafety *contagious*. The issues described in the following sections often result in *contagious unsafety*.

4.1 Unsynchronized Global State

The Rust equivalent of global variables are static items. These exist independently of any function scope for the entire duration of the program, and like normal variables, they can

either be non-mutable or explicitly marked as mutable. Since concurrent writes to a global variable are a source of data races, which is undefined behavior in Rust, *any* use of mutable statics is *unsafe*. Non-mutable statics are *safe* to access, but they require their types to be properly synchronized, which is indicated by the implementation of the Sync trait. An example is the Mutex construct, which, due to its synchronization mechanism, can provide safe mutable access to the inner variables even though it is not marked with the mut keyword.

When a programmer is mainly experienced in C or software is ported from C to Rust, using mutable statics for all global data might feel natural, making this a commonly used antipattern. The safe use of mutable statics requires the programmer to guarantee that no two mutable references to the static can exist at the same time. This guarantee is nearly impossible to uphold locally without synchronization, so the practice is generally discouraged.

In a project's context, the safety requirements might be fine since in initialization phases there might be only one thread and functions might drop mutable references before creating new ones. However, it is important that the memory safety of *safe* APIs does not depend on context. To be sound, they have to be safe, no matter the context and for all possible inputs.

Rust's standard library does not include bare-metal synchronization primitives aside from atomic types. Existing libraries [32, 33] provide a good starting point but do not fit our needs, as they are not minimal enough for us to easily verify or do not fit our bare-metal programming requirements.

Thus, we created a new collection of bare-metal synchronization primitives to aid in the migration from mutable statics to non-mutable statics: *hermit-sync*¹, partly building upon the existing libraries. These new synchronization primitives allowed us to replace mutable statics with non-mutable statics in our kernel, maintaining as little overhead as possible. We provide several flavors of synchronization primitives in the general categories inspired by the Rust standard library's assortment of OS-dependent synchronization primitives, as listed in Table 1.

The three mutexes are additionally available with interrupt safety: those variants temporarily disable interrupts while locked, avoiding deadlocks when accessing them from interrupts as well. SpinMutex and SpinRwLock are derived from the *spin* project [32], while PFLock is reexported from its original project [34] without modification. All mutexes and readers-writer locks implement the commonly used lock_api interfaces.

This new, unified, and diverse collection of synchronization primitives allowed us to replace mutable statics with

¹<https://github.com/hermitcore/hermit-sync>

Table 1. An overview of the available new synchronization primitives in *hermit-sync*.

Type	Description	Access Type	Size	Note
SpinMutex	A simple spinlock for no-contention scenarios	MutexGuard<T>	1 B	As fast as possible
TicketMutex	A ticket lock for scenarios requiring fairness	MutexGuard<T>	16 B	Fair
StillMutex	A mutex stub for discovering deadlocks in single-core scenarios (akin to RefCell)	MutexGuard<T>	1 B	Panics on contention
SpinRwLock	A simple spinning readers-writer lock for no-contention readers-writer scenarios	{Read,Write}Guard<T>	8 B	As fast as possible
PFLock	A phase-fair readers-writer lock for readers-writer scenarios that require fairness	{Read,Write}Guard<T>	32 B	Fair
OnceCell	A synchronization primitive that can be written to only once but requires no unlocking	&T	2 B	Write once, read forever
ExclusiveCell	A synchronization primitive that can be (mutably) accessed only once but requires no unlocking	&mut T	1 B	Write forever (one party)

non-mutable statics for global state in core parts of the Hermit kernel. By doing this, we created a foundation for further fulfilling the safety claims of many of our internal functions through analysis of the remaining *unsafe* code blocks.

Converting the mutable statics to non-mutable statics, utilizing these primitives for sound access, has revealed several potential concurrency issues. Before, there were no concurrency checks happening on any part of the global variable, and every use of mutable statics was simply marked as unsafe. The new design enabled compiler checks that allowed us to spot and address several issues when moving data across thread boundaries.

4.2 C-Style Abstractions

When transitioning from C to Rust, it is important to rewrite corresponding abstractions in sound Rust. Knowing the underlying hardware details, it might be tempting to translate C functions directly to unsafe Rust. However, this is prone to ignoring the implied invariants, such as the lifetime information of pointers. When writing such low-level abstractions, one must be cautious to document and satisfy all required safety invariants. Otherwise, the exposed API will not be usable in a sound way, even though the abstraction has been tested and appears to work.

In our kernel, the x86-64 paging abstraction was one such example. Developing a page table abstraction is a delicate task at the foundation of memory safety, potentially leading to hard-to-spot errors. The old implementation used the unsafe and incomplete *specialization* language feature, did not properly acquire and release utility pages, manually defined and often used architectural constants, did not properly define safety requirements, and often violated them as well. The old paging abstractions, with their undocumented and thus unsatisfiable APIs, inhibited the same type of contagious unsafety as mutable statics do.

```
struct InlineBumpAlloc {
    mem: [u8; SIZE],
    index: usize,
}

impl InlineBumpAlloc {
    // Returns a pointer that aliases `self.mem`!
    fn alloc(&mut self, Layout) -> *mut u8;
}
```

Listing 1. The old, unsound, bump allocator (simplified).

```
struct SliceBumpAlloc {
    mem: Cell<&'static mut [u8]>,
}

impl SliceBumpAlloc {
    // Creates slices without internal unsafety.
    fn alloc(&self, Layout)
    -> Option<&'static mut [u8]>;
}
```

Listing 2. The new, sound, bump allocator (simplified).

We rewrote our paging implementation using the existing abstractions from the `x86_64` crate. These abstractions properly encapsulate their internal unsafe usage of raw pointers and expose a designated set of APIs for allocating frames, pages, and the accompanying interactions. Contrary to our previous implementation, we did not find any soundness issues with the parts of the library that we used.

4.3 Aliasing Mutable References

One pattern to look out for is giving out raw pointers to memory that is also referenced mutably. As the raw pointers

are usually intended to be cast to references, this pattern results in multiple mutable aliases, violating Rust’s basic rules of memory safety.

This pattern was observed in our bootstrap allocator, which is a simple bump-allocator that works on a statically compiled memory pool included in the binary. The allocator abstraction contains the array from which it allocates memory, as shown in Listing 1.

Upon allocation, the function takes a mutable reference to `self` and thus to the whole memory pool but also returns a raw pointer to a part of that memory. Any use of that raw pointer would be undefined behavior, which means this API is not usable in a meaningful way.

Although a `UnsafeAliased` type is being proposed [35] that could allow for such a design, for now, we cannot have a mutably referenced allocator that owns its memory. Instead, our new allocator manages a mutable slice, as shown in Listing 2, which can be obtained, for example, from a statically allocated `ExclusiveCell`. Upon allocation, the allocator (safely) splits the internal slice `mem` into two slices, returns one of them, and updates the internal one with the second one, preventing any case of aliasing. Since the code for creating these references is completely written in safe Rust, the resulting code is automatically sound.

4.4 Reimplementing Memory Access

When implementing special kinds of memory areas, it is important to let the compiler help you when accessing the special memory—otherwise, it cannot check the memory’s access and synchronization requirements. That means, instead of accessing specific memory regions in assembly, creating and using references to the whole region is preferable.

We found this kind of issue in the *core-local storage* implementation, which is the CPU equivalent of thread-local storage, meaning each core has its own local version of some data. Because the compiler does not support this kind of special memory, which is only useful for kernels, we had to implement an abstraction ourselves. Similarly to how the FS register points to thread-local storage, we use the GS register for core-local storage.

The old implementation (Listing 3) was dispatched from one globally accessible mutable static. When accessing the individual fields via `get` and `set` from cores besides the boot core, the content was not read from the static but instead was read from a different memory location in assembly, derived from the contents of the GS register. This approach has three specific issues: it uses a mutable static (see subsection 4.1), it exposes an unsatisfiable unsafe function, and it changes memory behind a shared reference.

The new implementation (shown in Listing 4), replaces nearly all manual assembly memory accesses with Rust code. Moving threads that have references to the CLS to other cores is of no concern since Hermit, in its current design, does not move threads to other cores once spawned. We now provide

```
static mut CORE_LOCALS: CoreLocalStorage;

pub struct CoreLocalStorage {
    pub kernel_stack: CoreLocalVar<*mut u8>,
}

struct CoreLocalVar<T>(T);

impl<T> CoreLocalVar<T> {
    pub unsafe fn get(&self) -> T;
    pub unsafe fn set(&self, value: T) {
        // Derive member address from GS
        // Transmute `value` to `u64`
        // Store values using assembly
    }
}
```

Listing 3. The old core-local storage API (simplified).

```
struct CoreLocal {
    pub kernel_stack: Cell<*mut u8>,
}

impl CoreLocal {
    pub fn get() -> &'static Self {
        // Create reference from GS register
    }
}
```

Listing 4. The new core-local storage API (simplified).

a global function that creates a reference to the whole core-local storage struct from the GS register’s content. Instead of mutating data via a simple shared reference, individual fields can then be mutated via corresponding unsynchronized cell types, like `Cell` or `RefCell`, without any unsafe code after acquiring the core-local reference.

5 The Soundness Bootstrapping Problem

Despite our efforts, it is currently impossible to have a completely sound codebase on bare-metal systems without external input, as there is a fundamental *bootstrapping problem* with soundness. This is because the ownership system of Rust assumes that all resources come from outside the program and are simply managed by the code.

An easy example of this would be memory allocation, which would go as follows: The operating system provides heap memory to the central allocator, which can give ownership over memory to the application upon calling `malloc` and the application returns ownership by calling `free`. When trying to apply the same to bare-metal systems, the question arises as to how the allocator gets the memory for allocation. The simple approach would be to create a pointer to

a memory region and assume ownership. However, this is not sound, as a second allocator could be instantiated, taking ownership of the same memory region and thus breaking the memory rules of Rust. An approach to overcome this issue would be the use of a singleton pattern, preventing the creation of multiple instances of the allocator (a common pattern in embedded-rust development [36]). This provides a better and “safer” API and prevents major faults using this allocator. However, this does not create a watertight sound abstraction, as the code could still contain multiple types of allocators, each individually following said pattern. Nothing would hinder the user from instantiating two different allocators on the same memory region.

Another example we encountered were sound abstractions for hardware functionalities. We take the GS register as an example here. It is used to store the pointer to the thread-local storage and thus should only be written by the scheduler. A sound abstraction for this would be a proxy struct that has a safe function to write a value to the register, and only the scheduler holds ownership of that proxy. However, this only holds true as long as there is at most one of these proxy structs available in the code. Again, a singleton pattern can improve the situation but does not provide a safe abstraction, no matter how it is used.

The problem boils down to the necessity of ensuring single ownership for an existing hardware resource when there is no operating system taking on this responsibility. This is highly related to the known problem [37] that abstractions can be completely sound when used alone but unsound when used together.

To solve this issue, it would be sufficient to provide the application a single token from the outside, transferring ownership of all hardware to the kernel. The code jumping into the bare-metal application, be it C, Rust, or assembly, may create this token when jumping into the app. The only requirement is that the app is jumped into only once. An even simpler solution would be the usage of a two-stage startup process. A separately compiled code calling the application can create and provide a zero-sized token as an argument. However, it can be argued, if this soundness edge-case is worth the increased complexity in a real-world scenario. This and similar approaches of finding a new ownership root are subject to future work, as many of the implications are yet unclear.

6 Evaluation

It is in the nature of this work that evaluating the soundness of problems and solutions must be done on a case-by-case basis through a discussion (or even proof) of each improvement. Some soundness issues with the old abstractions have been discussed in section 4. To avoid repeating ourselves, we refrain from going over the already discussed topics again and skip a thorough discussion of all improvements here.

Type	Change
Functions	+3
Expressions	-405
Methods	-10

Table 2. The change in the kernel’s amount of unsafe code.

Figure 1. The change in unsafe expressions in our kernel for each pull request in the context of this work.

To provide a numerical result for this work, we analyzed the change in unsafe code in our kernel. This is done with a tool we created called *count-unsafe*² which counts several unsafety metrics for each Rust source file in a given path. In contrast to existing tools like *cargo-geiger*, this tool considers all architecture-specific code as well, which accounts for more than one quarter of our kernel’s lines of code. Our kernel rework to increase the soundness of the code was conducted in 24 separate pull requests and removed a total of 405 unsafe expressions and 10 methods in the codebase (Table 2). As can be seen in Figure 1, not every single pull request reduced the amount of unsafe code, as in some cases it was necessary to mark code as unsafe that was incorrectly marked as safe before.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have taken a look at the specifics of writing sound abstractions for *unsafe* Rust code in the context of operating-systems programming. Unsafe operations are necessary and useful for bare-metal programming, but one has to ensure that they cannot lead to undefined behavior, which could otherwise result in memory access bugs or even vulnerabilities. We argue that this principle should be followed from the start, as opting out of soundness considerations by “blindly” making abstractions unsafe is *contagious*.

²<https://github.com/mkroening/count-unsafe>

During our soundness rework of the Hermit kernel, we have identified four typical soundness issues and presented approaches to solve them: unsynchronized global state, C-style abstractions, aliasing of mutable references, and the manual reimplementations of memory access. As a result, we have reduced the number of unsafe expressions in the kernel by more than 400 and detected and removed several potential concurrency issues. As only parts of the codebase were investigated, a further reduction is expected.

A fundamental problem for soundness in bare-metal programs is the *bootstrapping problem*, as Rust's ownership system assumes that resources come from outside the program and are exclusive. We have outlined a solution for this problem, but there is room for further research on this topic.

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References

- [1] The Chromium projects authors. [n. d.] Memory safety. Publisher: The Chromium Projects. Retrieved Feb. 19, 2023 from <https://www.chromium.org/Home/chromium-security/memory-safety/>.
- [2] Paul Kehrer. 2019. Memory unsafety in apple's operating systems. Publisher: langui.sh. (July 23, 2019). Retrieved Feb. 19, 2023 from <https://langui.sh/2019/07/23/apple-memory-safety/>.
- [3] Evgenii Stepanov. 2020. Detecting memory corruption bugs with HWASan. Publisher: Android Developers Blog. (Feb. 13, 2020). Retrieved Feb. 19, 2023 from <https://android-developers.googleblog.com/2020/02/detecting-memory-corruption-bugs-with-hwasan.html>.
- [4] Gavin Thomas. 2019. A proactive approach to more secure code. Publisher: Microsoft Security Response Center Blog. (July 16, 2019). Retrieved Feb. 19, 2023 from <https://msrc.microsoft.com/blog/2019/07/a-proactive-approach-to-more-secure-code/>.
- [5] 2023. PYPL Popularity of programming language index. (July 2023). Retrieved July 31, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230728134343/https://pypi.github.io/PYPL.html>.
- [6] 2023. TIOBE index. TIOBE. (July 2023). Retrieved July 31, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230728134348/https://www.tiobe.com/tiobe-index/>.
- [7] 2023. Stack overflow developer survey 2023. Stack Overflow. Retrieved July 31, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230720043952/https://survey.stackoverflow.co/2023/>.
- [8] Graydon Hoare. 2016. Rust is mostly safety. (Dec. 28, 2016). Retrieved Aug. 1, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230607150946/https://graydon2.dreamwidth.org/247406.html>.
- [9] [SW] Jeremy Soller, Redox - Your Next(Gen) OS - Redox - Your Next(Gen) OS. URL: <https://www.redox-os.org/> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [10] Amit Levy, Bradford Campbell, Branden Ghena, Daniel B. Giffin, Shane Leonard, Pat Pannuto, Prabal Dutta, and Philip Levis. 2017. The tock embedded operating system. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM Conference on Embedded Network Sensor Systems (SenSys '17)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, (Nov. 6, 2017), 1–2. ISBN: 978-1-4503-5459-2. DOI: 10.1145/3131672.3136988.
- [11] Valentyn Valiaiev. [n. d.] Drone OS. GitHub. Retrieved July 31, 2023 from <https://github.com/drone-os>.
- [12] [SW] Cliff L. Biffle, Matt Keeter, and Bryan Cantrill, Hubris July 30, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/oxidecomputer/hubris> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [13] Kevin Boos, Namitha Liyanage, Ramla Ijaz, and Lin Zhong. 2020. Theseus: an experiment in operating system structure and state management. In 14th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI 20), 1–19. ISBN: 978-1-939133-19-9. Retrieved July 31, 2023 from <https://www.usenix.org/conference/osdi20/presentation/boos>.
- [14] Vikram Narayanan, Tianjiao Huang, David Detweiler, Dan Appel, Zhaofeng Li, Gerd Zellweger, and Anton Burtsev. 2020. {RedLeaf}: isolation and communication in a safe operating system. In 14th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI 20), 21–39. ISBN: 978-1-939133-19-9. Retrieved July 31, 2023 from <https://www.usenix.org/conference/osdi20/presentation/narayanan-vikram>.
- [15] [SW] Lachlan Sneff, gmorenz, and Gabriel de Perthuis, Nebulet July 18, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/nebulet/nebulet> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [16] [SW] Anhad Singh, Aero July 30, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/Anady-Python-Programmer/aero> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [17] [SW] John Hodge (Mutabah), "Tifflin" Experimental Kernel (and eventually Operating System) July 29, 2023. URL: https://github.com/thepowersgang/rust_os Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [18] [SW] Vincent Ollivier, MOROS: Obscure Rust Operating System July 28, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/vinc/moros> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [19] [SW] Steve Klabnik, Amit Levy, and Nabeel Omer, intermezzOS: kernel July 29, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/intermezzOS/kernel> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [20] [SW] Alex Chi Z, core-os-riscv July 26, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/skyzh/core-os-riscv> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [21] [SW] James Munns, tosc-rs/mnemos July 31, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/tosc-rs/mnemos> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [22] [SW] Gianmatteo Palmieri, Felix OS July 21, 2023. URL: <https://github.com/mrgian/felix> Retrieved July 31, 2023 from.
- [23] Stefan Lankes, Jonathan Klimt, Jens Breitbart, and Simon Pickartz. 2020. RustyHermit: a scalable, rust-based virtual execution environment. In *High Performance Computing (Lecture Notes in Computer Science)*. Heike Jagode, Hartwig Anzt, Guido Juckeland, and Hatem Ltaief, (Eds.) Springer International Publishing, Cham, 331–342. ISBN: 978-3-030-59851-8. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-59851-8_22.
- [24] Dinakar Dhurjati, Sumant Kowshik, Vikram Adve, and Chris Lattner. 2003. Memory safety without runtime checks or garbage collection. In *Proceedings of the 2003 ACM SIGPLAN conference on Language, compiler, and tool for embedded systems (LCTES '03)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, (June 11, 2003), 69–80. ISBN: 978-1-58113-647-0. DOI: 10.1145/780732.780743.
- [25] Ralf Jung, Jacques-Henri Jourdan, Robbert Krebbers, and Derek Dreyer. 2017. RustBelt: securing the foundations of the rust programming language. *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages*, 2, (Dec. 27, 2017), 66:1–66:34, POPL, (Dec. 27, 2017). DOI: 10.1145/3158154.
- [26] [n. d.] The rustonomicon. Retrieved Aug. 1, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230619130041/https://doc.rust-lang.org/nomicon/>.
- [27] Amit Levy, Michael P. Andersen, Bradford Campbell, David Culler, Prabal Dutta, Branden Ghena, Philip Levis, and Pat Pannuto. 2015. Ownership is theft: experiences building an embedded OS in rust. In *Proceedings of the 8th Workshop on Programming Languages and Operating Systems (PLOS '15)*. Association for Computing Machinery,

- New York, NY, USA, (Oct. 4, 2015), 21–26. ISBN: 978-1-4503-3942-1. DOI: 10.1145/2818302.2818306.
- [28] Amit Levy, Bradford Campbell, Branden Ghena, Pat Pannuto, Prabal Dutta, and Philip Levis. 2017. The case for writing a kernel in rust. In *Proceedings of the 8th Asia-Pacific Workshop on Systems (APSys '17)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, (Sept. 2, 2017), 1–7. ISBN: 978-1-4503-5197-3. DOI: 10.1145/3124680.3124717.
- [29] [n. d.] The rust reference. Retrieved Aug. 1, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230529125633/https://doc.rust-lang.org/stable/reference/>.
- [30] Unsafe code guidelines working group. [n. d.] Rust's unsafe code guidelines reference. Retrieved Aug. 1, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230522203232/https://rust-lang.github.io/unsafe-code-guidelines/>.
- [31] Boqin Qin, Yilun Chen, Zeming Yu, Linhai Song, and Yiying Zhang. 2020. Understanding memory and thread safety practices and issues in real-world rust programs. In *Proceedings of the 41st ACM SIGPLAN Conference on Programming Language Design and Implementation (PLDI 2020)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, (June 11, 2020), 763–779. ISBN: 978-1-4503-7613-6. DOI: 10.1145/3385412.3386036.
- [32] [SW] Mathijs van de Nes, spin-rs July 28, 2023. URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20230330163332/https://github.com/mvndnes/spin-rs> Retrieved Aug. 3, 2023 from.
- [33] [SW] Alex Kladov, Overview Aug. 4, 2023. URL: https://web.archive.org/web/20230324121527/https://github.com/matklad/once_cell Retrieved Aug. 4, 2023 from.
- [34] [SW] Claire Nord, PFlock: Phase-Fair Reader-Writer Lock July 31, 2023. URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20230804184231/https://github.com/cmnord/pflock> Retrieved Aug. 4, 2023 from.
- [35] Ralf Jung. [n. d.] UnsafeAliased: allow aliasing of mutable references · pull request #3467 · rust-lang/rfcs. GitHub. Retrieved Aug. 3, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230803071024/https://github.com/rust-lang/rfcs/pull/3467>.
- [36] Jorge Aparicio. [n. d.] Cortex-m documentation, peripheral struct. Retrieved Aug. 2, 2023 from https://web.archive.org/web/20230802194723/https://docs.rs/cortex-m/0.7.7/src/cortex_m/peripheral/mod.rs.html#167-175.
- [37] Ralf Jung. 2022. Soundness conflicts · issue #379 · rust-lang/unsafe-code-guidelines. GitHub. (Nov. 24, 2022). Retrieved Aug. 2, 2023 from <https://web.archive.org/web/20230315143826/https://github.com/rust-lang/unsafe-code-guidelines/issues/379>.